

BREAST CANCER

G.K. Qayumova

Deputy director for educational work of the Andijan branch of the Republican Center for training and specialization of secondary medical and pharmaceutical workers.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430775>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th November 2022

Accepted: 11th December 2022

Online: 12th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Breast, mammary glands, prolactin, oxytocin, hormones, growth, obesity.

ABSTRACT

This article talks about the issue of women's health, which is an integral part of society, and scientific approaches aimed at reducing their incidence of oncological diseases. In particular, we will talk about breast cancer, which has become one of today's hot topics, and measures for its early detection and treatment.

"We know a lot about the causes of cancer, it is necessary and necessary to put the fight against the tumor on the rails of prevention."

Academician N.N. Petrov is one of the founders of oncology.

Breasts are a pair of organs consisting of mammary glands, each woman has an individual shape, size and shape. Many women are not satisfied with the shape and size of their breasts. There are even unfounded opinions that women with small breasts have less milk. On the contrary, the size of the breast does not always indicate the abundance of milk. Milk secretion depends on the hormones prolactin and oxytocin, and in many cases, heredity. A woman should not only care about the appearance of her breasts, but also about her health. A woman's breast consists of mammary glands, which consist of 15-20 lobes. Each lobe has its own tributary, which is directed to the nipple. Under the skin of the breast is a layer of fat. Breast shape begins to sag with age. To

prevent it, you need to choose the right underwear and bras. According to research, one in eight women in the world will get breast cancer. 80% of women detect the first signs of this pain when palpating their breasts. Therefore, in order to prevent mammary gland diseases, a woman should regularly undergo a doctor-gynecological examination, and from the age of 20, she should examine her breasts every month. Breasts usually change their shape (swell, harden) during menstruation and hormones. Therefore, they should start checking measures on the 12-16th day of the menstrual period and two weeks after taking the medicine. Breast examination is carried out as follows: - Stand in front of the mirror and examine the breasts with the arms down. - Pay attention to the appearance of the breasts by raising the hands above the head. - Put your hands on your waist and tense your chest muscles. - This procedure can be done in the bath or shower, as the hands move lightly on wet skin. - A pillow is placed on the side of the

chest being examined. Raising the hands behind the head, with the other hand, the chest is palpated from the outside to the tip - clockwise. - The nipples are squeezed with thumb and forefinger. If the liquid is separated, pay attention to its color and consult a specialist-doctor. When the breasts are examined, attention is paid to the following changes: - changes in the shape and size of the breasts; - penetration into the nipples, roughness of the skin; - fluid leakage from the chest; - pain on palpation in the chest and armpits, clear feeling of lymph nodes; - redness and inflammation of the breast skin. If you notice such changes during the treatment, you should consult a doctor without panicking. There, you will be examined by qualified doctors using mammography and ultrasound. These methods are performed in low-level X-rays and are completely harmless to health. In general, because of the high incidence of breast cancer among women over 45 years of age, it is important to have an annual screening and mammogram to prevent the disease. If a cyst is found, the doctor will take fluid from the mammary gland through a special needle. If the liquid is colorless, it is found harmless and there is no need to continue the examination. On the other hand, if the fluid is not separated or colored, it is determined by biopsy (surgery). Diseases of the breast in many cases: - depends on heredity, that is, if women in your family suffer from these diseases, you are also at risk of developing them; - the risk of recurrence of the disease is 5 times higher in a woman who has previously suffered from a breast tumor compared to others; - in women with early onset of menstruation and late onset of climax; - measures to maintain insulin levels in the body of

patients with diabetes; - in women who gave birth after the age of thirty, never gave birth at all or had an abortion; - women who smoke tobacco and drink alcohol have a higher risk. Useful tips: Pay attention to your character: try to enjoy life, be cheerful. Strive to be among good-natured, world-viewing people who will be an example for you, to restore spiritual balance in the family! Take provitamins A, S, E, folic acid. Use vegetable oil in cooking as much as possible. Eat more chicken and fish.

Food should contain a lot of greens, tomatoes, cabbage, fruits and vegetables, soybean oil. Avoid the ultraviolet rays of the hot sun. Do regular physical education and training. Observe personal hygiene (using baby soap when washing softens the skin). Condensation of milk in the mammary glands. Condensation of milk in mammary glands, rupture of nipples and mastitis cause suffering in women. Dampness of milk: This is caused by improper milking, when the baby does not absorb enough milk. The milk ducts are blocked, the mammary glands become tense and painful. With this breast, the woman gently pulls the child when she is breastfeeding or milking. Cracked nipples: nipples are damaged during breastfeeding, dryness, and improper care of the nipples. The top of the teats cracks along the length and causes severe pain to the mother while breastfeeding. Due to severe pain, the mother becomes nervous, cries, as a result, her milk decreases. No matter how painful the mother is, she must endure and breastfeed from time to time. As soon as cracks or pain appear in the nipple, it is necessary to consult a doctor. Because through the cracks, germs can spread from the mother's hand or skin, from the child's

mouth, and inflammation of the mammary glands - mastitis can develop. In this case, the mammary glands become painful and hard. The pain intensifies, the glands tighten, the skin becomes red, the temperature rises, and the woman's condition worsens. It is not good to take self-medication measures (putting a hot lamp on the chest, doing ridiculous things: sprinkling ashes, putting on clothes, etc.). If the main cause is not identified, the hardened area softens due to the exacerbation of the disease. This is a sign of pus formation. In this case, it is necessary to immediately consult a surgeon, otherwise serious consequences may occur. Measures to prevent inflammation: - preparing the breasts for breastfeeding during pregnancy (massage, softening teats with chakanda or olive oil); - compliance with the rules of breastfeeding; - in the care of the breasts, follow cleanliness; - wearing a bra that lifts the breasts (milk stays when hanging); - protect hands from frostbite (do not wash diapers and diapers in cold water); - timely treatment of teat cracks (compress by adding honey in equal amount to egg yolk); - any disease that occurs in a nursing woman should be treated to the end. In many cases, after weaning the baby, the breasts become loose. As in the world, in Uzbekistan, breast cancer, followed by cervical cancer, is the most common cancer among women of all ages. Among women of all ages, breast cancer, stomach cancer, and cervical cancer are the third leading causes of death from diseases. Breast cancer is the most common tumor disease. According to medical statistics, 10% of women around the world are infected with this disease, especially women living in European countries. In most cases, cancer is observed

in people over 45 years old. In developed countries, this disease has decreased slightly, due to the invention of modern tests for the diagnosis of the disease and the effectiveness of treatment measures. Even so, the tumor is made up of different types of cells and their growth rates, so the treatment of the disease is difficult. The disease develops slowly, without symptoms for a long time, and in some cases, the disease can develop rapidly. Effective treatment of breast cancer is possible only in early detection. Although there are various reasons for the origin of cancer, the main place is occupied by genetic predisposition and hormonal changes, especially as a result of the influence of estrogenic hormones, the risk of tumor origin is high. After giving birth, the mammary glands prepare for breastfeeding, and if a woman does not breastfeed, the hormonal balance is disrupted, and changes in the tissues of the mammary glands also occur.

Attention! Research shows that taller women and overweight women are more likely to develop breast cancer during menopause.

The risk factors listed above do not directly cause a tumor, but simply increase the susceptibility to the development of cancer. In addition, not all tall and fat women get cancer. Of course, not one, but several factors play a role in the origin of breast cancer.

Like other tumors, breast cancer is difficult to detect in the early stages, because the disease begins without symptoms. If you notice any symptoms, such as pain in the breast, swelling, discomfort, enlarged nipples, pathological fluid leaking from the nipples, you should see a doctor immediately.

Attention! If you develop any hardened lumps on your nipples, see your doctor right away, even if you don't have any of the above symptoms.

A special table is used to determine the degree of the disease:

The number of primary tumors is indicated by the letter T, the number of metastases spread to other organs by the letter M, and the number of locally damaged lymph nodes by the letter N.

Low-grade tumors can be located in different areas of the breast: in the skin folds, around the areola and nipples, in the upper and lower inner square, or in the upper and lower inner square, in the rear axillary area.

Early diagnosis of breast cancer includes self-examination and examination by a

mammologist. If you are over 40 years old, you should have a mammography examination once a year.

It is better to independently check the breast every month, on the 5-7th day of the menstrual cycle. During the examination, it is necessary to pay attention to the symmetry of the mammary glands, the condition of the skin and teats, and the size of the mammary gland. Palpation can be done lying or sitting. Each breast should be palpated in turn, starting from the teats to the end of the body. Any stiffness and thickening of the breast should be a reason to suspect disease. In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the lymph nodes in the armpit area. If any suspected derivative is detected, it is necessary to immediately consult a specialist doctor.

References:

1. D.A. Asadov, N.Q. Murodkhodjaev - Oncology, Tashkent medical publishing house named after Abu Ali Ibn Sina, 2002 A.G. AHMEDOV
2. G.K. Ziyamutdinova -Anatomy, physiology and pathology Tashkent. "economy-finance" 2017
3. [http://www. minzdrav.uz./](http://www.minzdrav.uz/)- Republic of health care regulatory documents related to the system;
4. [http://www.ziyonet.uz./](http://www.ziyonet.uz/)
5. [http://www.referat.uz./](http://www.referat.uz/)